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Unique cellular network formation guided by heterostructures based on reduced graphene oxide - $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene hydrogels

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ABSTRACT

Two-dimensional (2D) materials remain highly interesting for assembling three-dimensional (3D) structures, amongst others, in the form of macroscopic hydrogels. Herein, we present a novel approach for inducing chemical inter-sheet crosslinks via an ethylenediamine mediated reaction between $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ and graphene oxide in order to obtain a reduced graphene oxide-MXene (rGO-MXene) hydrogel. The composite hydrogels are hydrophilic with a stiffness of ~20 kPa. They also possess a unique inter-connected porous architecture, which led to a hitherto unprecedented ability of human cells across three different types, epithelial adenocarcinoma, neuroblastoma and fibroblasts, to form inter-connected three-dimensional networks. The attachments of the cells to the rGO-MXene hydrogels were superior to those of the sole rGO-control gels. This phenomenon stems from the strong affinity of cellular protrusions (neurites, lamellipodia and filopodia) to grow and connect along architectural network paths within the rGO-MXene hydrogel, which could lead to advanced control over macroscopic formations of cellular networks for technologically relevant bioengineering applications, including tissue engineering and personalized diagnostic networks-on-chip.

Statement of Significance

Conventional hydrogels are made of interconnected polymeric fibres. Unlike conventional case, we used hydrothermal and chemical approach to form interconnected porous hydrogels made of two-dimensional flakes from graphene oxide and metal carbide from a new family of MXenes ($\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$). This way, we formed three-dimensional porous hydrogels with unique porous architecture of well-suited chemical surfaces and stiffness. Cells from three different types cultured on these scaffolds formed extended three-dimensional networks – a feature of extended cellular proliferation and pre-requisite for formation of organoids. Considering the studied 2D materials typically constitute materials exhibiting enhanced supercapacitor performances, our study points towards better understanding of design of tissue engineering materials for the future bioengineering fields including personalized diagnostic networks-on-chip, such as artificial heart actuators.

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1. Introduction

The discovery of graphene aroused an intense interest in two-dimensional (2D) materials [1,2]. Having access to a large variety of 2D materials discovered to date, researchers consider the formation of composite and hybrid materials with well-defined physicochemical properties superior to their parent 2D materials

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¹ Requests for biological data.

² Requests for materials.

[3]. Kim et al. described the general principles of the formation of three-dimensional (3D) architectures from 2D materials via self-assembly, which can be guided by using external stimuli, and the final structures can be strengthened by chemical cross-links [4]. The resulting architectures of such formed 3D structures are most crucial in the bioengineering field, where the cellular interactions depend strongly on the resulting material's mechanical properties, pore structure and surface chemistry [5–7]. On one hand, solely the hydrated polymeric networks with high water content (> 90%), i.e. hydrogels, can resemble ideal micro-environments for cell culture applications [8]. On the other hand, 2D materials have the potential to alter the physicochemical properties of hydrogels, such as mechanical performance [9,10] and conductivity [11], as well as adding binding sites for bio-functionalization to regulate cell behaviour, including proliferation, differentiation and protein synthesis to promote specific tissue regeneration [5,12–14].

The newest family of 2D materials beyond graphene-derivatives is transition metal carbides, carbo-nitrides and nitrides, known as MXenes [15,16]. Those MAX phase-derived materials can exist either in the form of accordion-like multi-layered structures or graphene-like few/single-layer flakes [17]. Regardless of the form taken, the MXene's structure is composed of inner transition metal layers and an outer transition metal oxide / hydroxide outer layer covered with oxygen/hydroxyl and fluorine surface terminations. The combination of hydrophilicity and, in some cases, high metallic-like conductivity has attracted a worldwide interest in MXenes and their possible applications [18].

The MXene $Ti_3C_2T_x$ was the first to be discovered and is by far the most thoroughly investigated and best understood member of the MXene family, with a promising performance in a plethora of applications, ranging from energy storage to photo-thermal anti-cancer therapies [19–21]. MXene cytotoxicity and biocompatibility were confirmed *in vitro* and *in vivo*, showing dependence between the form (multi- / single-layered), oxidation state (pristine / oxidized) and concentration [22–25]. Pristine, single-layered $Ti_3C_2T_x$ flakes are highly compatible with different cells and can be applied as cultured cell scaffolds [22]. For example, these flakes have been used in conjunction either with biopolymeric hydrogels to form photothermally responsive materials by being encapsulated in poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAM) [26], or with cellulose to form 3D scaffolds releasing Doxorubicin on demand for anti-cancer therapies [27]. Recently, Pan et al. presented the integration of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ flakes with 3D printed bioactive glass scaffolds for simultaneous bone-tumour killing by photonic hyperthermia and bioactive glass-induced bone-tissue regeneration [28]. The implanted 3D bioactive glass component assisted the differentiation of human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells into osteoblasts forming a dual-functionality scaffold. Biodegradation products from $Ti_3C_2T_x$, Ti-based species, accelerate the formation of a new bone and lead to bone-tissue reconstruction. Simultaneously, hyperthermic response leads to eradication of bone-tumour tissue. Similarly, recent efforts of Driscoll et al. show that the cortical rat neurons, cultured on $Ti_3C_2T_x$, are as viable as those in control 2D cultures, and they are able to adhere, grow axonal processes with synaptic presence and form functional networks for the formation of high-resolution neural interfaces [29].

Some 2D materials can be used not only as nano-fillers but also to form 3D structures for cell growth and proliferation [30,31]. For example, it was shown that neural stem cells, cultured within 3D graphene scaffolds, formed neuro-spheres, unlike 2D graphene films. Graphene has also been used to form 3D interconnected graphene-carbon nanotube webs, where the co-cultured and fluorescently labelled glioma and healthy cortical cells with different colours enabled an investigation into glioma infiltrations, forming a bioengineered 3D cortex-like networks model [32]. This suggests

certain advantages of 3D architectures over classical 2D substrates [33]. However, there are currently no universal 3D models allowing investigations across multiple cell types.

Herein, for the first time, we prepared an efficient framework for the formation of 3D cellular networks on composite hydrogels on the basis of hydrothermal synthesis of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ with graphene oxide. These kinds of composite hydrogels have already been shown to exhibit capacitance of up to $370 F.g^{-1}$ at $5 A.g^{-1}$ and $165 F.g^{-1}$ at $1000 A.g^{-1}$ [34]. Here, three different human cell line types of different origins were chosen: tumorigenic neuron-like neuroblastoma cells (SH-SY5Y), epithelial adenocarcinoma cells (HeLa) and non-tumorigenic fibroblasts (MSU 1.1). Apart from the comprehensive characterisation of the 2D materials; their 3D forms; and their cytotoxic influence on the aforementioned cell lines, the most innovative part of this work lies in the formation of cellular networks under fluorescent microscopy on days 2 and 7 of cell cultures, which is linked to the unique structural stability and surface chemistry provided by rGO- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ composite hydrogels. F-actin immunocytochemistry staining fluorescence microscopy was used to determine not only the cells' morphologies but also whether the cells can attach, proliferate, migrate and interact within the rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels and form extended proliferated cellular networks. This step is a pre-requisite for fabrication of cellular organoids/3D cell culture models for screening various diseases.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

The graphite powder, sodium nitride (99%) and ethylenediamine (>99.5%) were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrochloric acid (35–38%), sulfuric acid (95%) and hydrogen peroxide, H_2O_2 solution (30%) were obtained from POCH (Gliwice, Poland). Potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$) was purchased from J.T. Baker. Lithium fluoride (LiF) 98.5%, Ti, Al, and TiC powders were purchased from Alfa Aesar. All the solutions were prepared using ultrapure MilliQ ($13.4 M\Omega cm^{-1}$) type 1 water (H_2O).

2.2. Preparation of graphene oxide (GO) flakes

Graphene oxide water dispersion ($4 mg.mL^{-1}$) was prepared by the modified Hummers method [35]. Briefly, 1 g of graphite powder and 0.5 g of $NaNO_3$ were mixed in the beaker, followed by an addition of 23 mL of H_2SO_4 (95%) and left for 1 h while being magnetically stirred (300 rpm). The solution was cooled down in an ice bath, and 3 g of $KMnO_4$ was gradually added to the suspension to prevent the risk of overheat and explosion. The mixture was stirred at $35^\circ C$ for 12 h. It was then diluted with 500 mL of H_2O under constant stirring, and 4.6 mL of H_2O_2 (30%) was added to complete the reaction. Such prepared mixtures were washed with HCl (1%) and H_2O multiple times, followed by purification via dialysis for a week in order to remove the remaining impurities.

2.3. Preparation of Ti_3C_2 MXene flakes

The preparation of the $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene monolayers started with Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase powder. The Ti_3AlC_2 was synthesized by mixing TiC, Al and Ti powders in molar ratios of 2:1.05:1, respectively. The mixed powders were ball milled at 300 rpm for 24 h and then heated to $1550^\circ C$ for 2 h under argon flow. The MAX phase sinter was milled into powder using a TiN-coated end mill on a drill press. The resulting powders were sieved through a 400 mesh sieve and collected for further experiments. The formation of MXenes involved etching out Al from MAX phase powder using LiF and HCl solution. Briefly, 1 g of LiF was dissolved in 10 mL of

12 M HCl. Next, 1 g of the Ti_3AlC_2 powder was slowly added to the solution. The solution was stirred for 24 h at 35 °C and 300 rpm. Subsequently, the solution containing multi-layered MXenes was transferred into a centrifuge tube, and 30 mL DI water was added. After centrifugation at 3500 rpm for 10 min, the supernatant was discarded and the washing process was repeated several times until the pH of the solution was near neutral. Then, the solution was sonicated under Ar flow for 1 h in a sonication bath. In order to avoid the oxidation of MXenes, the temperature of the bath was kept below 20 °C using ice. Finally, the solution was centrifuged for 1 h at 5000 rpm, and the supernatant containing MXene flakes ($8.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was collected and stored under Ar for further use. The detailed morphology of obtained MXene flakes using the same method can be found in our previous report [22].

2.4. Preparation of rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels

For the fabrication of the hydrogels, we started with monolayer GO flakes of lognormal distribution sizes of $2 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene monolayer flakes with lognormal distribution sizes of $600 \pm 500 \text{ nm}$. Full characteristics of both types of flakes can be found in Supporting Information (Figs. S1 and S2) and in our previous reports [22,30]. The rGO hydrogel was prepared by filling 25 mL glass vial with 20 mL of graphene oxide solution ($4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). In the case of rGO-MXene hydrogel, 5 mL of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ suspension ($8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was added to 10 mL of GO suspension ($4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) and filled up to 20 mL with H_2O into the same 25 mL glass vial. Both vials were placed on magnetic stirrers at 150 rpm under bubbling Ar flow. 60 μL of ethylenediamine was slowly pipetted into each vial. Finally, the vials were placed in Teflon lined autoclave reactors, sealed under Ar and placed in an oven at 95 °C for 6 h. Both autoclave reactors were left overnight to cool down. After the vials were removed from autoclaves, the supernatants were decanted, and as-prepared hydrogels were transferred to freshly H_2O filled Falcon tubes (50 mL) and sealed under bubbling Ar prior to their use.

2.5. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The samples were mounted onto the sample holder by a double-sided tape (SCOTCH). The XPS measurements were carried out with the PHI 5000 VersaProbe II XPS system (Physical Electronics) with monochromatic Al- K_{α} source (15 kV, 50 W) and photon energy of 1486.7 eV. All the spectra were measured in the vacuum of $1.2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Pa}$ and at the room temperature of 21 °C. The analysed area on each sample was a spot 100 μm in diameter. The survey spectra were measured with a pass energy of 187.850 eV and electronvolt step of 0.8 eV. Dual beam charge compensation was used for all the measurements. The spectra were evaluated with the MultiPak (Ulvac - PHI, Inc.) software. All binding energy (BE) values were referenced to the adventitious carbon C1s peak at 284.80 eV.

2.6. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed using PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer ($\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation). The geometry of the diffractometer is a Bragg-Brentano with 0.01° step size and the angular range of measurements was from 5° to 60° . The GO, MXenes and EDA treated MXene solutions were dragged and dropped onto a Si holder and dried at 40 °C overnight before the measurements. The hydrogels were dried overnight at 40 °C; such obtained xerogels were then wetted with H_2O so that they could be stuck to the Si holder. It was found that the XRD patterns of the wetted xerogels were changing because of evaporation of the solvent during the measurement (Fig. S4).

Therefore, we performed multiple measurements with pattern recording every 90 s up to 0.5 h.

2.7. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

JEM-7001TTLS (JEOL Ltd., Akishima, Japan) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was used to investigate the morphology and chemical composition of all the samples. The morphology and structure of the GO flakes were measured with the accelerating voltage of 15 kV and the MXene flakes with the accelerating voltage of 10 kV.

The rGO and the rGO-MXene hydrogels were examined by the same microscope in addition to using a PP3000T (Quorum Technologies, Laughton, UK) cryo-SEM preparation system by which the cryo-specimen was prepared, processed and transferred into the SEM chamber, finally allowing direct observation of the sample in the vitrified state. In this case, the sample was mounted on a metal holder and cryo-fixed by being plunged into sub-cooled nitrogen, N_2 (N_2 slush, at the temperature of -210°C). Then the sample was transferred under vacuum to the preparation chamber located on to the SEM. Inside the preparation chamber, at -180°C , the specimen was fractured to expose a fresh inner surfaces. Then it was sublimated and coated with a thin platinum layer. Finally, the sample was loaded under vacuum into the SEM cryo-stage (-190°C), where the surfaces were imaged. The imaging, as well as elemental analysis (of all cryo-prepared hydrogels), was performed at the accelerating voltage of 15 kV.

Statistical analysis of the pore size was performed manually from over 400 pores across the collected images. The pores shapes were approximated by ellipses, with two radii (the meridian (A longest) and the equatorial axis (B shortest) being assigned, starting from the meridian and then perpendicularly drawing an equatorial line in image].

2.8. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectrum was taken on a Renishaw Raman imaging microscope (inVia) equipped with a Leica microscope (50 × objective) and a CCD detector. The Raman spectra of all samples were recorded using a $\lambda = 785 \text{ nm}$ laser (with $1200 \text{ l}\cdot\text{mm}^{-1}$) with the power kept below 0.1 mW to avoid thermal degradation of the samples. The Raman data were acquired as a line mapping (10 s integration time, 3 accumulations, 5 points taken). The spectra were processed in Wire software WiRE™ 3.0 software. 50 μL of $4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ GO and MXene were drop-casted on a Si(111) substrate and left overnight to dry under vacuum. Such prepared rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels were dried overnight under vacuum at 40 °C, and then pressed into an Al foil.

2.9. Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

The AFM measurements were performed using the Icon Scanning Probe Microscope (Bruker). The GO sample was spin coated on a Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) substrate using a POLOS spin coater. The Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) substrates were first cut into 1 cm² pieces, then cleaned in acetone; DI water; and ethanol by the aid of sonication, and finally oven dried. The GO or MXene water dispersion of $0.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ was then deposited at 3000 rpm and at an acceleration of $300 \text{ rpm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ to cover the Si/SiO₂ with a monolayer of GO flakes. The latter were scanned in air at room temperature using tapping mode with antimony (n-type) doped Si tips (RTESPA-300, f: 300 kHz, 40 N/m—Tapping mode). The images were acquired at 1024×1024 pixels resolution over $80 \times 80 \mu\text{m}^2$ for GO or $93 \times 93 \mu\text{m}^2$ areas for the MXenes at a scan rate 0.5 Hz. The images were 2nd order flattened using Nanoscope software.

2.10. Rheology

The rheological measurements were performed on a RheoStress RS150 Haake rheometer using plate-plate arrangement with a top plate 20 mm diameter and a 3 mm gap. The hydrogels were carefully placed on the bottom plate using a spatula, and subsequently the top rheometer plate was slowly lowered to the desired gap in order to minimize sample disruption. Frequency sweeps were performed from 0.1 to 100 Hz at 1% strain within the linear viscoelastic regime of the samples. The frequency sweep was also performed immediately after the first one on the same sample to assess sample damage/recovery. All the measurements were performed at room temperature (RT = 21 °C) and repeated at least two times to ensure reproducibility.

2.11. Cell culture

Human cell lines: fibroblasts (MSU-1.1), epithelial adenocarcinoma (HeLa) and neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y) were cultured in sterile cell culture flasks with Dulbecco's modified Eagle's culture medium (DMEM, Gibco) supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma-Aldrich), 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg.mL⁻¹ streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich). The cells were cultured at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ for 24, 48 and 72 h. The medium was removed after reaching about 80% confluency, and the cells were washed with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS, Sigma-Aldrich) followed by sub-cultured by trypsinization (a mixture of 1% Trypsin-EDTA (trypsin-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) in PBS). The cell suspension was then counted using TC10TM automated cell counter (BioRad). The experiments were performed using cultures in the same range of passages (3–6).

2.12. Viability tests

The cytotoxicity assay was performed to assess the cytotoxic effect of the flakes (GO, MXene and GO-MXene) and the 3D scaffolds (rGO / rGO-MXene hydrogels), along with determining their possible biocompatibility towards human cell lines (HeLa, MSU-1.1, SH-SY5Y). The quantitative determination of the cell viability after their culture for 24, 48 and 72 h with GO and MXene, and GO-MXene flakes and both positive (10% DMSO in DMEM) and negative controls (cell seeded in empty non-treated plastic well) was evaluated by measuring the ability of mitochondrial reduction of WST-1 to a coloured (dark yellow) formazan product by mitochondrial succinic dehydrogenase. The cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^4 cells per well in the sterile 96-well plates and incubated overnight at 37 °C in humidified conditions. The next day the cell culture medium was replaced with 100 µL of fresh media containing increasing concentrations of MXenes and GO-MXene in 50:50% mass ratio (1, 5, 10, 50, 100 µg mL⁻¹). The cells without addition of any flakes were taken as a negative control. For a positive control, the medium was replaced with DMSO (10% - DMSO in DMEM). After 24, 48 and 72 h, 10 µL of Cell Proliferation Reagent WST-1 (CELLPRO-RO ROCHE, ThermoFisher) was added to each well and incubated for an additional 2 h at 37 °C. The absorbance of all the samples was then measured at $\lambda=450$ nm (with $\lambda=630$ nm background) with a spectrophotometer (Biochrom Anthos Zenyth 340 Microplate Reader). For the viability assay assessment of the cytocompatibility of 3D rGO and rGO-MXene scaffolds, we carefully cut the hydrogels with a scalpel to a cylindrical shape of a height of ~5 mm so that they would accurately fit the 96-well plates (with $d = 6.9$ mm). All the tested hydrogels were washed in PBS and sterilized prior to the cell culture using UV irradiation ($\lambda=254$ nm) for 30 min and placed in sterile 96 well plates, followed by cell seeding at density of 1×10^4 cells/well. After 24, 48

and 72 h of incubation, the cells were processed, as we described above. All the experiments were done in triplicates ($n = 3$).

2.13. Confocal microscopy

To evaluate the cell morphology by F-actin detection, we seeded human cell lines (MSU, HeLa, SH-SY5Y) on the rGO and rGO-MXene scaffolds. After sterilization, the rGO and the rGO-MXene were carefully cut with a scalpel to a cylindrical shape of a height of ~5 mm so that they would accurately fit the 96-well plates (with $d = 6.9$ mm). Then MSU, HeLa and SH-SY5Y cell lines were initially seeded separately at a concentration of 1×10^4 cells per well. Over the period of 7 d of culturing, the medium was changed every 2 d. After 2 or 7 d in culture, the cell medium was removed, and the samples were transferred to Lab-Tek-8 well chamber slides, washed then twice in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, Sigma Aldrich) and fixed in 3.7% paraformaldehyde in PBS solution. Then, all the samples were permeabilized by 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS. For F-actin cytoskeleton visualization, Oregon Green 488 Phalloidin (Thermo Fisher Scientific) solution in PBS containing 1% BSA was added to each well and incubated for 20 min at room temperature (RT = 21 °C). The solution was then removed, and the samples were again washed twice in PBS. Finally, for cell nuclei visualization, the samples were incubated with DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-fenylindol) (Thermo Fisher scientific) solution for 5 min at RT = 21 °C. The stained cells on the rGO and the rGO-MXene hydrogels were then imaged immediately under a confocal laser scanning microscope (Zeiss LSM 780) with an excitation laser wavelength at $\lambda = 488$ nm and peak emission measured at $\lambda = 520$ nm and $\lambda = 360$ and $\lambda = 460$ for actin and nuclei, respectively. 40 × water objective with the numerical aperture of $n = 0.95$ was used for all the images. Supporting videos of confocal Z-stack of MSU, HeLa and SH-SY5Y cell cultured on the rGO and the rGO-MXene scaffolds after 2 and 7 days in culture were performed at a series of confocal planes. A 3D reconstruction was performed using ZEN 2010 software (Carl Zeiss). All the experiments were repeated in triplicates ($n = 3$).

2.14. Statistical methods

All the values were presented as mean ± standard deviation. The statistical unpaired *t*-test was performed between each pair of values (in Origin 2016). The test results * denotes significant differences at $p < 0.05$, while ** indicates significant differences at $p < 0.01$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure and chemistry of composite hydrogels

Ti₃C₂T_x MXene flakes were prepared via Al-atoms removal from Ti₃AlC₂ powder using a LiF:HCl etching solution [36]. This process led to the formation of a few- or single-layered flakes possessing mixed surface functionalities including -O-, -OH, and -F (Fig. 1). In the case of GO, the typical fabrication procedure included oxidation of graphite, which resulted in the formation of GO flakes with the surface covered with hydrophilic groups =O, -OH, -COOH (Fig. 1) [5,35]. Thanks to the availability of the functional groups present on both 2D materials, ethylenediamine (EDA) molecules were used to cross-link the neighbouring flakes by strongly interacting with O containing moieties (typically with -O- of MXenes and =O and -COOH of GO). The hydrothermal treatment of GO led to reduction and cleavage of the functional groups, resulting in the formation of a reduced graphene oxide (rGO) [37]. The degree of the rGO reduction depends on the applied temperature, which typically ranges from 90 °C to 180 °C.

Fig. 1. A) Scheme showing reaction between the EDA, GO and MXene flakes. B) Photographs of GO, rGO-MXene and MXene hydrogels after their reaction. Background is ruler paper where smallest square is 1 mm². Raman spectroscopy of C) GO flakes, MXene flakes, rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels with, D) detailed zoom is at 100–1000 cm⁻¹. E) Wide XPS scan of the rGO, rGO-MXene and MXene dried hydrogels. F) XRD patterns of GO and MXene flakes and rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels.

In order to avoid oxidation of the MXenes, all the hydrothermal processes were conducted at 95 °C for 6 h (Fig. 1A), according to a single-step facile approach used by Chen et al. [38] and Li et al. [39]. The simultaneous chemical inter-sheet crosslinking of the individual flakes and reduction of graphene oxide induced by EDA-mediated reaction allow fabricating the rGO, the rGO-MXene and the MXene hydrogels. In our procedure, we used constant flake concentration of 4 mg.mL⁻¹ in 20 mL of H₂O. It is the lowest initial concentration enabling formation of stable hydrogels based on GO, hereafter referred to as rGO hydrogels (Fig. 1Bi), which retained their fidelity after the fabrication procedure. To fabricate rGO-MXene hydrogel, we used 2 mg.mL⁻¹ of each GO and MXene flakes, overall giving 4 mg.mL⁻¹ of flakes, the same as for each flake attempt. The composite hydrogel based on GO and MXene flakes is hereafter referred to as rGO-MXene

(Fig. 1Bii). The hydrogels formed solely from 4 mg.mL⁻¹ MXene flakes (Fig. 1Biii) visually appeared to be in a semi-collapsed state. This effect is directly related to the availability of the reactive surface functionalities, the concentrations of which, in the case of the GO flakes, are significantly higher, compared to the MXene flakes.

Due to difficulties during the formation of stable pure Ti₃C₂T_x hydrogels, they were not further tested. Further characterisation of the materials was conducted on GO/MXene flakes and rGO/rGO-MXene xero- and hydrogels.

In line with expectations, the GO was partially reduced to rGO as a result of the hydrothermal process. This is evidenced by the slight increase in the characteristic ratios of the intensity of D (1349 cm⁻¹) to G (1595 cm⁻¹) Raman scattering bands from I_D/I_G = 1.15 for GO flakes, to 1.19 for rGO-MXene hydrogels

(and typically observed 1.25 for pure rGO film) (Fig. 1C). The higher I_D/I_G ratio after the reduction of GO is typically observed in the samples reduced via the hydrothermal process. This effect is related to the removal of oxygen functional groups and the decrease in the average size of the sp^2 domains [40]. MXenes exhibit several E_g and A_{1g} active Raman modes, which are related to a vibrational response of Ti2 (terminal external Ti atoms), C, O and F atoms in MXene Ti-bonded functional groups: F_2 , O_2 , $(OH)_2$, and $O(OH)$ (Fig. 1D). The presence, the intensity and the position of Raman bands are related to the type and the concentration of functionalities [41]. For the wavelength, λ of 785 nm, based on our previous research, we correlated nine active Raman modes with MXene terminal moieties [42]. Modes I (121.9 cm^{-1}), II (201.1 cm^{-1}), III (246.7 cm^{-1}) and VIII (618.1 cm^{-1}) correspond with the vibrations of Ti2/C/F atoms, confirming the presence of $Ti_3C_2F_2$. Modes IV (283.1 cm^{-1}), VI (513.6 cm^{-1}) and VII (589.9 cm^{-1}) are related to the vibrations Ti2/C/O/H atoms of $Ti_3C_2(OH)_2$ and $Ti_3C_2O(OH)$. The remaining V (363.9 cm^{-1}) and IX (724.2 cm^{-1}) modes indicate the presence of $Ti_3C_2O_2$ by vibration of Ti2/C/O and Ti2/C, respectively. Thus, based on the Raman spectra, the presence of the aforementioned functionalities in MXene and rGO-MXene samples was confirmed. Additionally, the presence of these functional groups was confirmed for both samples via X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements (Fig. 1E).

The typical crystallographic structures of pure constituent flakes, i.e., GO and MXenes, were confirmed by XRD (Fig. 1F). The reduction of GO via EDA-assisted hydrothermal process resulted in the disappearance of the sharp GO-related peak at $2\theta = 11.29^\circ$ and the appearance of rGO-related (002) broad peaks at $2\theta = 11^\circ$ and 23.50° . The presence of (002) peak in the rGO xerogel pattern indicates that the rGO framework is composed of few-layer stacked graphene sheets with poor ordering [43]. In the case of the rGO-MXene xerogel, the typical MXene-related peak (002) was shifted toward lower values - from $2\theta = 6.88^\circ$ to 6.38° . At first, we supposed that this effect was related to the presence of the rGO layers separating the MXene flakes. Interestingly, the XRD pattern of rGO was highly dependant on the hydration of the material (Fig. S3). The disappearance of the rGO-related (002) peak in rGO-MXene xerogel XRD patterns confirmed the efficient dispersion of single rGO nanosheets in the hydrogel structure [44,45].

The functional groups located at the edges of rGO and MXene flakes contributed to the strong interconnection of the flakes forming a porous hydrogels network with large pores (Fig. 2A-D). Furthermore, the temperature mediated reduction of GO flakes to rGO typically increases their hydrophobicity and the π -conjugated structures of rGO because of the partial removal of the oxygen-based functionalities [38]. The cryo-SEM images of rGO hydrogels showed a very strongly interconnected network with many straight-accordion like regions (Fig. 2A), which ultimately contributed to the elasticity of the overall bulk hydrogel. Statistical analyses performed over an ensemble (with over 400 individual random pores taken into account) of cryo-SEM images (Fig. S4) revealed the average (taken from both the meridian (y longest) over the equatorial axis (x shortest) values) pore size of both rGO ($6 \pm 4\ \mu\text{m}$) and rGO-MXene ($7 \pm 5\ \mu\text{m}$) hydrogels. On the other hand, as expected, the structure of the rGO-MXene hydrogel appeared to be partially disrupted with fewer inter-pore connections than in the case of the rGO (compare Figs. 2D and 2C), confirming the partial fidelity of bulk structure (Fig. 1B) and lower degree of inter-flakes crosslinking despite the similarities in pore-sizes. The tendency for the formation of larger accordion-like bundles of flakes was lower for the rGO-MXene hydrogel, suggesting successful mixing of the two flakes and formation of heterostructures (Fig. 2B). Energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyses further confirmed the presence of Ti in the rGO-MXene hydrogels during in-situ cryo-imaging (Fig. 2E-F).

The unique build-up of the obtained architectures of chemically crosslinked hydrogels is reflected in their overall elasticity, as measured by oscillatory rheology (Fig. 2G). Both compositions exhibited typical characteristics of gel-like behaviour with $G' > G''$. As expected from the observed degree of crosslinking and known high stiffness of individual rGO flakes [46], at $44 \pm 8\text{ kPa}$, the rGO hydrogels exhibited higher storage moduli values than those measured on the rGO-MXene hydrogels with moduli of $19 \pm 1\text{ kPa}$. Upon immediately repeating the measurement, the respective moduli were reduced to $40 \pm 6\text{ kPa}$ and $18 \pm 2\text{ kPa}$.

We hypothesize that this could have happened owing to the fact that MXenes can remain hydrophilic after the temperature-mediated process with higher propensity to recover to the original hydrated structure, whereas upon shearing, the rGO hydrogel can irreversibly lose non-chemically crosslinked structural domains due to loss and rearrangement of solely physically (hydrophobic and π - π stacking) bound flakes [18]. Further investigations into molecular and structural integrity of these gels under shearing are outside the scope of the current article, despite being highly interesting.

3.2. Biocompatibility of rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels

In our previous research, we described the cytotoxicity of GO and $Ti_3C_2T_x$ flakes [22,30]. Prior to performing the biocompatibility tests on our hydrogels, we investigated the cytotoxicity of the constituent MXene and GO-MXene flake dispersions used for their preparation, with a full description available in Supporting Information (Fig. S5). Briefly, we observed profound dose-dependant cytotoxicity of pure MXene flakes but significantly lower toxicity of mixed GO-MXene flakes (1:1 wt ratio, the same as the one used for fabricating hydrogels), toward human fibroblasts (MSU1.1), neuronal-like (SH-SY5Y) and epithelial adenocarcinoma HeLa cell lines. The cells viability after exposure to 1, 5, 10 $\mu\text{g.mL}^{-1}$ of both GO-MXene and MXene flakes during all periods of time was found to remain around 80%. However, the higher dosages of 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g.mL}^{-1}$ induced significant ($p < 0.05$) decreases in the cell viability, even below 40% in the case of the HeLa cells ($p < 0.01$) for the highest MXene concentration.

Next, we cultured three cell lines: epithelial adenocarcinoma (HeLa), neuronal-like (SH-SY5Y) and human non-tumorigenic fibroblasts (MSU 1.1) on the rGO and the rGO-MXene hydrogels to look at any possible cell type-cytotoxicity relationships. The viability of all cell types, cultured for 24 h on both rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels, remained at the similar level of $> 95\%$ (Fig. 3A).

After 48 h of culturing, the viability of all cell types, compared to controls, decreased by about ~ 10 – 15% ($p < 0.05$) for both hydrogels with no significantly visible differences across the three cultured cell types (Fig. 3B). After 72 h, all cells cultured on the rGO-MXene hydrogel retained 75–80% viability with no visible differences across cell phenotypes, whereas a significant difference ($p < 0.01$) was observed for the cells cultured on the rGO hydrogel with the viability of HeLa cells of 66%, compared to $\sim 85\%$ for the SH-SY5Y and MSU 1.1 cells (Fig. 3C). It follows that the typically durable and prolific HeLa cells are more sensitive to the rGO than the other cell lines [47]. HeLa cells also showed the lowest viabilities when cultured with pure aqueous GO or GO-MXene flakes mixtures (Fig. S5). It is worth noting that the dose-dependant cytotoxic effects induced by 2D MXene and GO-MXene flakes are higher than those of the 3D architectures fabricated by the hydrothermal method. This was already observed in our previous work focused on hydrothermally fabricated rGO structures [30]. This effect is related to the unique architecture, topography and chemistry of fabricated porous hydrogels, which appear to resemble native extracellular matrix (ECM) environments well. Although previous reports suggest that MXene flakes could undergo envi-

Fig. 2. Cryo-SEM images of A) / C) rGO hydrogel and B) / D) rGO-MXene hydrogel. EDS elemental analysis of E) rGO hydrogel and F) rGO-MXene hydrogel. G) Storage (G') and loss (G'') modulus obtained at 1 Hz and 1% strain from oscillatory rheology frequency sweep for rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels. Frequency sweeps were immediately repeated on the same samples to assess their recovery capabilities after initial frequency sweeps from 1 to 100 Hz. Values are represented as mean \pm SD.

ronmental oxidation in the culture media, which is believed to be the main source of their cytotoxic effect [24], it has been recently shown that polyphosphate ions, such as those present in the PBS or cell culture medium, can cap MXene edges and protect flakes from undergoing environmental oxidation [48]. Similar syntheses show lack of oxidation of rGO-MXene hydrogels for supercapacitor electrodes, where any impurities would lead to impeding the capacitance storage performance [34,49]. We therefore believe that in our case the $Ti_3C_2T_x$ flakes covalently bonded to the rGO counterparts are stable and protected against oxidation, yet their functional groups are uniquely suited to induce enhanced cell adhesion, proliferation, migration and cellular networks formation.

3.3. Cellular networks formation on rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels

To determine the morphology of the cultured cell lines and whether they could attach; proliferate; migrate; and interact within the rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels, actin filaments (F-actin) staining and DAPI fluorescence assays were performed (Fig. 4–6). Images with separated channels are included in the supporting information (Fig. S6–S8). After 2 d of culturing, the cells were able to proliferate and fill the spaces inside the porous hydrogels.

3.3.1. Cellular networks of HeLa cells

It was found that the cultured HeLa cells proliferated poorly on the rGO scaffold with apparent weak cellular interactions

Fig. 3. Viability of cultured HeLa, SH-SY5Y and MSU cells at A) 24 h, B) 48 h and C) 72 h on rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels measured by using WST-1 reagent. Negative and positive controls were flask containing free cells and cells cultured in medium containing 10% DMSO in DMEM, respectively. An asterisk (*) indicates significant differences at $p < 0.05$, two asterisks (**) indicate significant differences at $p < 0.01$, whereas ns indicates that results are not statistically significant. Unless comparison is drawn between two sets, symbol means the comparison was made to control (C⁻). Single legend for all graphs is provided in the middle of Figure. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(Fig. 4, S6). This was rather surprising since it is established that HeLa cells adhere and spread more efficiently on stiffer substrates with elasticities between 40 and 85 kPa [50]. It is therefore reasonable to conclude that the surface chemistry-related cytotoxicity of rGO (or GO) flakes toward HeLa cells is more important than the substrate stiffness, which results in their poor viability, proliferation, adherence and weaker ability of migrating through the hydrogels with minimal number of cells found within the pores [51].

The proliferation of cervical cancer cells cultured on the rGO-MXene hydrogel was more pronounced and the cells were found well distributed throughout the scaffold. It is known that cells of various types prefer to attach to the high-surface area of 2D materials, both in 2D and in 3D environments [7,9,52]. Again, considering the known affinity of HeLa cells for higher stiffness structures [50], counter-intuitively HeLa cells appeared to have attached to the surface of softer and more hydrophilic rGO-MXene interconnecting elements (surfaces) and migrated through the pores inside the scaffold forming extended connections and network with the neighbouring cells. These cells showed characteristically rounded morphology—a large amount of cortical actin and a small number of cellular processes [53]. The morphology of the spreading cells and their connections suggested their high adaptation to the three dimensional architecture of the rGO-MXene hydrogel, indicating its better suitability for HeLa cells in comparison to the rGO.

Our data show that the HeLa cells cultured for 7 d on the rGO scaffolds were not able to actively grow and proliferate (Fig. 4, S6). Although the HeLa cells cultured on the rGO were visible, the spreading efficiency was not as effective as in the case of our rGO-MXene hydrogels. On the other hand, the HeLa seeded on the rGO-MXene grew in clusters tightly connected to the neighbouring cells, for which a large amount of cortical actin structures is typical. The cells proliferated less effectively on the rGO-MXene after 7 d than after 2 d. The migration of the HeLa cells through the rGO and the rGO-MXenes was not as effective as in the case of MSU and SH-SY5Y cells, thus no supplementary movies of confocal Z-stack of HeLa F-actin and nuclei are provided.

3.3.2. Cellular networks of SH-SY5Y cells

In the case of the rGO, neuroblastoma cells were found to have an immense propensity to self-assemble inside the scaffolds' pores (Fig. 5, S7) and form structures that are quite similar to pre-organoids (Supplementary Movie SM-S1). Neuroblastoma cells had typical spheroid morphologies, with a clustered organisation, and grew in the form of tightly packed spherical constructs, quite similar to the cells in a neuro-sphere system [54]. Many tight cell junctions between the neighbouring cells were visible. In fact, the neuroblastoma cultured on the rGO showed an abundance of cells in clusters placed in larger pores of the rGO hydrogel (SM-S2). Cellular colonies had size ~120 μm and contained approximately

Fig. 4. Immunofluorescent images of HeLa cells cultured for 2 and 7 d on glass, rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels. Cell nucleus and F-actin were stained, by DAPI (blue) and Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin (green), respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

~150 cells. Due to their stem-like cell origins, neuroblastoma cells are able to trigger neuro-sphere formation. It was shown that the neuro-sphere formation was significantly improved by the combined treatment of 13-cis-retinoic acid (RA) with the proteasome inhibitor MG132, because of the differentiation and the increased apoptosis, which led to a reduced tumour volume [55]. Marrella et al. showed that neuroblastoma cells cultured within 3D alginate-based hydrogels present a spheroid morphology with optimal survival and proliferation [56]. On the other hand, the neural stem cells seeded in the 3D scaffolds made of a graphene foam (3D-GF) showed an increased neuro-sphere formation, compared to the 2D graphene films (2D-GF), owing to the topographical features of 3D-GF [31]. Such elevated clustering of neuroblastoma on the rGO hydrogel, compared to rGO-MXene hydrogel, stems from the higher stiffness of the gels with a unique chemical composition and scaffold architecture. Then again, SH-SY5Y seeded on the rGO-MXene hydrogel featured many typical characteristics for neuroblastoma, such as elongated, polarized morphology with long neurites [57]. The cells exhibited extended migration through architectural network elements, leading to their propensity for formation of extended three-dimensional networks (SM-S2). These data suggests that it is possible to choose the type of the desired cellular network (between spheroid-like cultures on rGO and extended protruding networks on rGO-MXene) via replacing the constituent 2D materials forming hydrogels.

Neuroblastoma cells cultured for 7 d on the rGO started to spread further to deeper parts of the scaffold and resembled the

Fig. 5. Immunofluorescent images of SH-SY5Y cells cultured for 2 and 7 days on glass, rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels. Cell nucleus and F-actin were stained, by DAPI (blue) and Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin (green), respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

extended networks instead of the spheroids observed after 2 d (Fig. 5). The longer incubation time resulted in higher proliferation and migration and possible differentiation of neuroblastoma cells. It is well known that during culturing and differentiation, spheroids migrate and spread from the original aggregates [58]. Here, we observed that the neuroblastoma cells started to migrate widely in random directions of the hydrogel scaffolds after 7 d of culturing on the rGO hydrogels. However, migration and cellular connections of SH-SY5Y through the rGO hydrogels were not prominent compared to rGO-MXene; therefore, we only show supplementary videos of confocal Z-stack of neuroblastoma F-actin and nuclei on rGO-MXene scaffolds. The same cells cultured on the rGO-MXene started to grow into clusters over time and formed more compact colonies with a high number of viable neuron-like cells interconnected to each other by long neurites (SM-S3). The neuroblastoma cells also appeared to have their characteristic morphological features with polarized, elongated morphology and long cellular projections towards neuronal type, as we described previously [59]. However, extended investigations into the differentiation process fall outside the scope of this current article and will be pursued in future.

3.3.3. Cellular networks of MSU 1.1 cells

Fibroblasts cultured on the rGO and the rGO-MXene hydrogels, attached and colonized on scaffolds, are the most effective and rapid amongst all studied cell types. (Fig. 6, Fig. S8). The MSU 1.1 cells seeded on the rGO hydrogel were found to have a higher

Fig. 6. Immunofluorescent images of MSU 1.1 cells cultured for 2 and 7 d on glass, rGO and rGO-MXene hydrogels. Cell nucleus and F-actin were stained, by DAPI (blue) and Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin (green), respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

amount of possible F-cortical actin without cytoplasmic projections, suggesting different morphologies from the control cells. Depending on the cell type, the function of cortical F-actin is associated with various processes such as involvement in transportation, this being a barrier or a scaffold in neural and neuroendocrine cells [60]. Fibroblasts also grew densely packed with tight connections to the neighbouring cells. The cells formed highly-interconnected 3D network protruding the structure of the hydrogel (SM-S4).

The MSU 1.1 cells seeded on the rGO-MXene hydrogels for 2 days were observed in an elongated and polarized morphology with long cytoplasmic projections (lamellipodia) (Figs. 6, S8). The cells displayed appropriate morphological features with prominent stress fibres and F-actin dense protrusions, strongly suggesting adhesion and enhanced cell migration within the hydrogel structure [61]. Moreover, many cell-cell junctions linked the actin cytoskeletons of adjacent fibroblasts forming extended cellular 3D architecture networks of rGO-MXene hydrogel (SM-S5). The cells penetrated further within the rGO-MXene scaffold, simultaneously showing a higher degree of cell connectivity between the adjacent pores, compared to the rGO hydrogel (compare Fig. 6 and SM-S4–6).

After 7 d culturing of the fibroblast cells on the rGO hydrogel, the cells exhibited limited growth and migration when compared to the 2 d culture. For this reason, we only show a supplementary video of confocal Z-stack of MSU cells F-actin and nuclei penetrating only the rGO-MXene scaffolds. Compared to 2 d culture, MSU 1.1 cells had a proper elongated morphology (right-most column

in Fig. 6). Fibroblasts cultured on rGO-MXene adhered and widely spread along the pores and the structure of the scaffolds. MSU 1.1 tended to form cell colonies inside the pores and spread deeper throughout the scaffold, as evident in SM-S6. Under a confocal microscope, the number of visible fibroblast cells was found to be significantly higher on the rGO-MXene than on the rGO; however, the cells seeded on both types of hydrogels had a typical elongated morphology, with many cell projections (lamellipodia, and filopodia) indicating active migration (Fig. 6 and SM-S6). In summary, the cells exhibited better adhesion, morphology and migration on the rGO-MXene hydrogels than on the rGO, which relates to more hydrophilic MXene built-up flakes present in the heterostructure. Our findings are supported by the research conducted by Vlček et al. [62]. In their work, they compared HeLa cells adhesion in 2D system on GO and graphene supports. It was found that oxygen functionalities present on the GO surface are potent cell adhesion enhancers in comparison to bare graphene surfaces. Although a bare graphene surface attracts more relevant biomolecules and proteins such as collagen, vitronectin, fibronectin and laminin, their functional forms are impeded by strong hydrophobic attractions. Even though hydrophilic surfaces have lower adsorption affinity to those biomolecules, the functional forms of proteins remain less affected and enhance the promotion of cellular processes. Thus, keeping in mind that MXenes are more hydrophilic than rGO due to the presence of plethora of unreacted -OH groups [18], we observed a similar effect in our 3D systems.

4. Conclusions

In summary, here we developed a temperature mediated chemical crosslinking process that led to the formation of two hydrogels with unique 3D architectural characteristics and chemistries. The first—a rGO-based hydrogel—had a more hydrophobic surface and was stiffer with elastic moduli of the order of ~40 kPa. The second—a rGO-MXene-based hydrogel—had a more hydrophilic surface and was softer with elastic moduli of ~20 kPa. Independently, three human cell lines (HeLa, SH-SY5Y and MSU 1.1) of a different origin exhibited a tendency to form extended 3D cellular networks on the rGO and the rGO-MXene hydrogels, as evidenced by fluorescent confocal microscopy images and supporting movies. We also show self-assembly of structures that are quite reminiscent of neuro-spheres from SH-SY5Y cells after 2 d on the rGO hydrogels, which then de-assembled into diffusive extended cellular networks after 7 d of culture.

The architectures of the fabricated scaffolds allow diffusion of nutrients and promote cells migration throughout the hydrogels. All types of cultured cells exhibited high inter-pore penetration capabilities, as evidenced by the extended formation of migration-driven cell cytoskeleton features (neurites, lamellipodia and filopodia). This phenomenon appears to be far more evident in the rGO-MXene hydrogels than in their rGO counterparts, leading to hitherto unobserved distinctive cell type-independent cellular interactions with the $Ti_3C_2T_x$ flakes. This suggests their unique biological activity and a promising future use in tissue engineering and personalized medicine fields. Although cellular *in vitro* responses were coherent on these hydrogels, histocompatibility profiles would certainly differ on tissues of different types or under *in vivo* conditions. In spite of the fact that the safe *in vivo* use of 2D materials has yet to be explored, these hydrogels open up a new, prominent perspective for organ-on-a-chip technologies.

Author contributions

J.K.W. and B.S. designed the concept of the study. J.K.W. performed atomic force microscopy, rheology and XPS measurements, wrote the original draft and coordinated the preparation of the

final manuscript. B.S. fabricated hydrogel samples and characterized materials using Raman spectroscopy. J.L. performed biological experiments. V.N. prepared the MXenes. K.T. provided GO and performed SEM analysis on GO and MXene flakes and hydrogels. C.A. performed XRD measurements. B.P. performed cryo-SEM measurements of hydrogels. M.W.B. and M.O. participated in meritorical discussions and revised the manuscript. All authors commented and have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.actbio.2020.08.010.

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